

SAMR MODEL: CLARIFICATION OF AMBIGUOUS TERMS

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ABSTRACT

In the rising trend of applying Information Communication Technology (ICT) into teaching, ICT integration means much more than simply using Power Point slides, software like Hot Potatoes, or platforms like Facebook or Moodle in teaching and learning. Therefore, many scales have been designed to guide teachers in the evaluation of their ICT integration, and one of which is the increasing popular model of SAMR. Interesting as it seems, but the SAMR model proves to be a weak framework to base on for this evaluation. This study points out how inconsistent the interpretation of the SAMR is in the literature and point out what should be done to improve the model for measuring the levels of ICT use of language teachers. The study proposes an understanding of tasks which include textbook tasks, teaching tasks, and learning tasks, and attempts to modify the terms of “functional changes”, and “task redesign” to help distinguish different levels of ICT integration in the model.

Key words:SAMR, levels of ICT integration

1 THE SAMR MODEL

Dr. Ruben R. Puentedura developed the SAMR model in 2006 aiming at improving educational quality by integrating technology into teaching in the state of Maine in the US. SAMR distinguishes two main categories of ICT use namely Enhancement and Transformation. Enhancement levels comprise Substitution and Augmentation levels while Transformation levels consist of Modification and Redefinition levels. It serves as a framework for the evaluation of how much learning is transformed thanks to the use of mobile technology in teaching (Romrell, Kidder, & Wood, 2014), or what the pedagogical functions of mobile devices are (Van Oostveen, Muirhead, & Goodman, 2011). Besides, SAMR approaches ICT integration in separate tasks, not the lesson as a whole (Hilton, 2016), and thus helps teachers in directing their ways of selecting and integrating technological tools in teaching practice (Hartmann & Weismer, 2016). Additionally, SAMR describes a set of criteria for judging what extents the technology integration teacher can employ to improve the existing learning tasks (Hos-McGrane, 2014). Therefore, it is expected to be used in assessing levels of technology integration in classroom teaching, which range from enhancing the traditional tasks or activities to creating new and innovative ones (Amer & Ibrahim, 2014).

The SAMR model is illustrated in the diagram below

Figure 1: The SAMR model

(Puentedura, 2006)

In general, for the Substitution and Augmentation levels, the use of technology is considered as the enhancement for the available learning tasks, “replacing and improving the existing tools” (Hilton, 2016, p.69), adding motivation and creating interest for learning. For this category, some activities can still be fulfilled without new technology. On the other hand, for the Modification and Redefinition levels, the alternation of the existing teaching and learning activities is considered as the Transformation which goes beyond the original forms. Indeed, a complete invention of new learning tasks or activities are required to partially or entirely transform the available task (Hilton, 2016).

Puentedura (2013) suggested the inquiry to recognize the move from one level to another as follows.

- Substitution:
 - What will I gain by replacing the older technology with the new technology?
- Substitution to Augmentation:
 - Have I added an improvement to the task process that could not be accomplished with the older technology at a fundamental level?
 - How does this feature contribute to my design?
- Augmentation to Modification:
 - How is the original task being modified?
 - Does this modification fundamentally depend upon the new technology?

- How does this modification contribute to my design?
- Modification to Redefinition:
 - What is the new task?
 - Will any portion of the original task be retained?
 - How is the new task uniquely made possible by the new technology?
 - How does it contribute to my design?

2 VARIATIONS IN UNDERSTANDING SAMR LEVELS

Despite having the guided questions of Puentedura (2013), the identification of activities circumscribed within a specific level of SAMR still varies in many studies using this scale as a framework for measuring ICT integration. This variety is shown in the summary practical technology-integrated activities in teaching with their explicit categorization of four levels according to the SAMR model across different types of publications in the table below.

Table 1: Summary of technology uses in different publications based on the SAMR model

Levels of ICT integration	Examples of teachers' and students' use of ICT	Publications
Substitution	Teachers use ICTs to prepare lecture notes, assignments and examinations, to give PowerPoint presentation, to give students materials, and take their assignments online, to communicate with students via emails, Facebook, or phones, to suggest the use of e-books, to teach using interactive boards, or to make audio or video record of lectures to give to students before class.	Jude, Kajura, and Birevu (2014)
	➤ Teachers upload syllabus as a Word document on to a course site, take printed assignments instead of hand-written ones, and use e-books with highlighting and commenting function, and giving online class meetings instead of face-to-face classes.	(Lund, 2015)
	➤ Students take note with a device when learning	(Pride, 2016)
Augmentation	➤ Teachers use search engines to search for information, check words' meaning, collect content for lesson plans, use Spell check, thesaurus, track changes in Microsoft Word to edit texts, use citation tools like Endnote, use Google doc to share documents and encourage collaborative work, use bulk messaging to contact	Jude et al. (2014)

Levels of ICT integration	Examples of teachers' and students' use of ICT	Publications
	students, use plagiarism detection software, use different videos to illustrate different case studies, use blog to discuss topics with students before class, and use Skype to teach when off campus.	
	➤ Teachers give and collect online quizzes and assignments	Lund (2015)
	➤ Students keep a co-constructed online document.	Pride (2016)
Modification	➤ Teachers assign students internet-based research topics, use open educational resources, create group discussions online, use MUELE as a platform to organize courses, use cellphones to support students academically, use content authorizing software to create interactive learning materials, use Facebook to interact, use online assessment tools, and use video conferencing tools.	Jude et al. (2014)
	➤ Students use blogs and wikis for peer review and collaborative writing	Lund (2015)
	➤ Students use mind-mapping software online to create multimedia-rich presentations.	Pride (2016).
	➤ Teachers send SMS of short reading messages to students to encourage them to read ➤ Students make recording of talks on different topics to share with the whole class online.	(Hockly, 2012)
	➤ Teachers develop mobile tags with QR codes or social bookmarking to trigger communication of areas of interests: knowledge, language competence, or the way to use mobile devices. ➤ Teachers make learning contracts to encourage learning inside and online outside the class ➤ Students collaboratively redesign activities and methods to improve communicative skills.	Abdullah, Siraj, and Hussin (2014)

Levels of ICT integration	Examples of teachers' and students' use of ICT	Publications
Redefinition	➤ Students discuss and make notes from discussions on MUELE, use open resources as teaching and learning materials, and use games in lessons.	Jude et al. (2014)
	➤ Students make videos and share online	Lund (2015)
	➤ Students make a book trailer, engage in a virtual England in the Elizabethan time using Google Cardboard.	Pride (2016)
	➤ Students make video presentations and post them online for peer comments and teacher evaluation	Abdullah et al. (2014)
	➤ Students do video conferencing with peers and teachers via communication tools to enhance communicative skills	
	➤ Students participate in synchronous and asynchronous forum on different topics	
	➤ Students play educational mobile games individually or collectively.	
➤ Students post reflections on academic acquisition and future learning goals		
➤ Students go around the town taking digital pictures of historical landmarks and then use them to create a multimedia interactive quiz for other students	Hockly (2012)	
➤ Students use the application Comic Strip It and the tablets' camera to create a comic strip.	Fabian and MacLean (2014a)	
➤ Students use the tablet camera to take pictures around the campus and use and the Skitch application to compile them into a message and present in class.		

As can be seen in table 1, levels of ICT integrations in teaching are sometimes differently interpreted. Lund (2015) sorts the online class meetings into Substitution level, arguing that this is just a simple alternation of space and time, not the function of face-to-face lectures. However, Jude et al. (2014) consider this as an activity at Augmentation level which can be done through Skype when the teacher is off campus.

Moreover, Jude et al. (2014) classify the use of Google documents to encourage collaborative

learning at Augmentation level while a similar activity of using Wiki or blog to stimulate students comments and exchanges online is considered by Lund (2015) as at Modification level. Jude et al. (2014) also seem to conflict with themselves by asserting the use of Facebook for academic exchanges to be at the Modification level, when its function is more or less to either replace face-to-face communication at Substitution level or to encourage collaborative learning from students as seen in the use of Google documents that they sort at Augmentation level. Besides, Hockly (2012) puts into Modification level the students' activity of sharing recordings of their individual speeches online. Meanwhile Abdullah et al. (2014) consider a similar activity of making and sharing video presentations online for peer comments at Redefinition level. In these cases, the mere difference in the two activities is the inclusion of the function facilitating peer comments. Moreover, in another case, the same use of video conference tools to develop communicative skills for students is considered at different levels of the SAMR model, in particular at Modification by Jude et al. (2014), but at Redefinition level by Abdullah et al. (2014).

In short, the inconsistency in the interpretation of the SAMR model prompts a necessity to have the modification of the model to curb its misunderstanding and misuse.

3 SUGGESTIONS FOR UNRAVELLING THE INCONSISTENT INTERPRETATION OF SAMR LEVELS

This section will point out solutions to the current problems of the SAMR model and then attempts to rearrange conflicting ICT uses in section 2 above.

3.1 How terms and their relationships should be understood in the SAMR model

The ambiguity of special terms in the SAMR model causing confusion can be addressed by chopping inclusive terms into smaller components. Some terms in the model have not been broken down into details, which causes ambiguity in understanding the broad and multi-component terminology. For instance, teachers may not know what "task redesign" means because the word "task" is inclusive of teachers' professional tasks other than teaching, teaching tasks, learning tasks and textbook task. Therefore, teachers may not know which task the model is mentioning in the term "task redesign". Some tools will allow the redesign of one task while others can assist the creation of other tasks. However, it should be understood that these tasks may have very strong connections, and even inseparable in some cases especially the teaching and learning tasks in class. Therefore, there are cases where teacher's uses of technology are considered for evaluation with the SAMR in isolation from other tasks, which at times gives inadequate hint for the job. An example is the use of Power Point in teaching. If Power Point is mentioned in isolation with textbook tasks and learning tasks, then it can simple be considered as a Substitution for board and chalk use. However, it is at Augmentation level or higher when there are multimedia contents and additional functions or task redesign brought about by the internet-connected computer which empowers the teaching and learning activities. Therefore, to evaluate the use of Power Point, the purpose of use, its design, its functions, and its prompts for learning activities should all be considered.

Besides, the relationships between terms in the model should be explained. In the model, the

concept of “task” only appears in the Modification and Redefinition levels, and that of “functional changes” only applies to technological tools in Substitution and Augmentation levels. However, if the technological tool has other functions compared to older tools such as the inclusion of a countdown timer, grammar error checking, or internet connections, these functional changes will eventually alter the teaching and learning tasks. In other words, tasks and tools’ functional changes have a reciprocal bond. Therefore, both the functional changes of the technological tool and alterations of the tasks are supposed to be taken into consideration in evaluating the teacher’s level of ICT integration in all levels of the SAMR model for a more well-rounded evaluation. That approach will point out whether a functional change is a standalone or incorporating factor besides other changes ICT uses bring. In addition, although the emphasis of the SAMR model is on the enhancement and transformation of learning (Chou, Block, & Jesness, 2012; Hos-McGrane, 2014; Romrell et al., 2014), if the textbook tasks and teaching tasks are excluded, then when it comes to identify functional changes of such cases as teachers’ use of Power Point presentation instead of writing on the board, there will be no room for learning tasks to be discussed, and thus only partial evaluation of this ICT use can be made with the SAMR model at Substitution level. In contrast, in the same case, teaching tasks or textbook tasks can be analysed to see the improvement with hyperlinks or multimedia content embedded in Power Point slides which are based on to consider Augmentation or higher levels. However even when the notion of “task” have covered all three components of teaching tasks, learning tasks, and textbook tasks with their mutual relationships, some cases of ICT uses can still be inadequately assessed by the SAMR model. An example of it is the teacher’s use of Facebook closed groups to communicate with students. In this example, it is clear to sort this activity into the Augmentation level when Facebook allowsthe function of commenting or discussing around the clock from every class member is added into the communication. However, that is only the cursory evaluation which can change when other factors are considered. Indeed, the level of this ICT use can be at Modification level if it is done regularly to aim at promoting written discussions to practice students’ writing skill. The task redesign in this case is the inclusion of more authentic situations for writing practice encouraged by the change of the serious classroom environment to a more casual cyber space. In brief, for ICT use of teachers to be accurately evaluated, its effect on tools’ functions, teaching task, learning tasks, textbook tasks, and other out-of-class activities of the teacher to improve teaching and learning should be taken into account. These relationships among the tasks are described in figure 2 below with all of the teacher’s use of ICT inside and outside the classroom considered for ICT integration level with the SAMR model while the crossed section (irrelevant to teachers’ ICT use) is excluded from the SAMR model.

Figure 2: The relationships of tasks for the SAMR model

Furthermore, task redesign, the factor that improves ICT integration from Enhancement to Transformation levels, need more guideline to facilitate the understanding of the SAMR model. From the perspective of a language teacher, a revisit to Table 1 above indicates a convergence of features of technology use that promotes: (1) students' use of technological skills (in using mind-mapping software, creating video presentations, making audio stories or videos about given topics), and (2) authenticity of the learning task (in making videos about current situations in society, in having video projects in groups, and in talking about different topics which are commented by friends), and (3) language skills integration (in reading about the topic, writing up content for their presentations, videos or audio recordings to share with the class)

In addition, it is the ways the tool is used, not the tool itself, that decide the level of ICT integration. Functional changes should be understood as additional functions enabled by the new tool compared to the traditional tools for teaching. When the tool is merely a substitution for traditional books and board, and the teacher does not make use of its advanced function, the ICT integration is only at Substitution level, but when it prompts changes in functions and task redesign, it will be upgraded into higher levels. Therefore, functional changes should be considered wider in relation to task redesign to see if such change can add any new learning and additional features of the aforementioned tasks. For example, the functional change of a textbook task reveals when e-books are used instead of paper books to enable different functions of the mobile devices including new word checking, highlighting, and commenting. These are functional changes of the e-book, but they clearly entails additional teaching and learning

activities for the class. In brief, information about what tool teachers use and how they use it to bring in new functions or additional activities should all be considered for a comprehensive evaluation of ICT integration level using the SAMR model.

3.2 How conflicting cases of ICT uses could be rearranged

With the understanding of “task”, “functional changes”, and “task redesign” of the SAMR model above, cases of inconsistency in the interpretation of the four levels can be resolved as follows:

Inadequate description of how ICT uses affect teaching and learning tasks has prevented the search for entailed function changes or task redesign. In particular, the organization of online class meetings, Skype meetings or video conferences cannot be measured because there is no information about what people do in such meetings and what changes in functions of tasks, or in task redesign these meetings create.

As for cases that have adequate information for evaluation, the assortment is summarized below.

Table 2: Rearrangement of ICT uses according to the modified SAMR model

SAMR level	ICT use	Reasons for the ranking
Modification level	Google documents, blogs or Wiki for collaborative learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Functional changes: students’ simultaneous participation in the co-construction of a product. This enables convenient peer comments instead of having everyone waiting for one person to finish writing the comment on a joint writing product. - Task redesign: The Google document requires collaborative learning at all time, so even when students perform their individual task, they need to look at what their friends have produced and keep their product unified. For blogs and Wiki, besides finishing the assignment as usual, students have to take the role of a publisher for their work.
Redefinition level	The share of video presentation online	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New task: making videos and sharing them online are new learning tasks for most classes indisputably. - Task redesign: in-class presentations are turned into out of class video presentations. Also, this task requires students to integrate technological skills.

4 CONCLUSION

The study elaborates the problems in understanding and using the SAMR model as a measuring tool for language teachers’ ICT integration levels, and then addresses this trouble by singling out individual factors that make the model user-unfriendly. As a result, it suggests the creation of an

expanded description of SAMR focusing on identifying the scope of “tasks” (out-of-class teachers’ tasks to improve teaching and learning, teaching tasks, learning tasks, and textbook tasks), the features of “functional changes” (the addition function of the new tool compared to the old tool, and the additional teaching and learning activities this new function entails), and the components of “task redesign” (the addition of requirement of students’ use of technological skills, more authenticity, and language skills integration). Especially, in order to use SAMR as a measuring tool of ICT integration level, the description of how the tool is used and how it relates to teaching tasks, learning tasks, and textbook tasks. Only then can functional changes, task redesign, and new tasks be identified.

This study features a library research on SAMR model; therefore, it is just limited within the available cases of ICT integration in a part of the literature about the model. It would be better done in a further study on ICT practitioners to find out what teachers focus on the most when using a technology in teaching and which set the foundation for the identification of the factors that should be included in SAMR levels. Then also research should explore how teachers evaluate the importance of different factors brought to teaching and learning by ICT integration such as authenticity, integrated language skills and students’ technological skills. Only then can the SAMR model be closer to the main drive behind ICT integration and present better description of its levels for more consistent use of the model as a gauge for teachers’ ICT use and as a guideline for their professional development.

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